

NEW PERIOD AND SOCIAL HISTORICAL ASPECTS OF LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Аннотация. Мақолада мустақиллик йилларида ўзбек тили борасида олиб борилаётган сиёсат, ўзбек тилининг бугунги ҳолати очиқ берилган. Ўзбекистонда миллий масалалар, айниқса, тил масалалари минтақадаги бошқа давлатлар билан солиштирганда демократик тамойиллар асосида, бағрикенглик билан йўлга қўйилганлиги халқаро ҳамжамиятлар томонидан эътироф этилганлиги ёритилган. Ушбу мақолада ўзбек тили борасида жамиятда мавжуд муаммолар таҳлил қилинган ва уларнинг ечими таклиф этилган.

Калит сўзлар: Ўзбекистон, тил, сиёсат, тарих, она тили, миллий тикланиш.

Аннотация. В статье раскрывает процессы возрождения узбекского языка в годы независимости Узбекистана. Было подчеркнуто, одна из главных сторон менталитета узбекского народа толерантность, имеющая глубокие исторические корни, проявляющая себя и в годы независимости Республики Узбекистан. В данной статье анализируются проблемы, существующие в обществе относительно узбекского языка, и предлагаются пути их решения.

Ключевые слова: Узбекистан, язык, политика, история, родной язык, национальное возрождение.

Annotation. The article reveals the processes of the revival of the Uzbek language during the years of independence of Uzbekistan. It was emphasized that one of the main aspects of the mentality of the Uzbek people is tolerance, which has deep historical roots, which manifests itself during the years of independence of the

Republic of Uzbekistan. This article analyzes the problems that exist in society regarding the Uzbek language, and suggests ways to solve them.

Key words: Uzbekistan, language, politics, history, native language, national revival.

Language is a significant asset to a nation, embodying Benazir values and representing a priceless heritage. It reflects the history and culture of the people and elites who created it. In many countries, the state language is used to regulate government affairs, maintain records, and document history in a standardized manner, reflecting the interests of the indigenous population of the region. The state language can be officially designated through legislation or by popular recognition. In some countries where there is no specific law regarding the state language, it is determined by popular recognition, and state work is conducted in that language.

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The history of the language, its formation, and development from a normative point of view cannot be studied without considering the history of the nation. In this regard, researching the socio-philosophical and conceptual foundations of the development of the state language from today's perspective is becoming increasingly important.

For many years, world science has studied the development of national languages as state languages from philosophical, political, legal, linguistic, and other perspectives. Such studies aim to find effective mechanisms for problem-solving. However, in practice, the relationship between the state language and national languages is maintained according to the principle of linguistic diversity, either by granting state status to one or more languages in a particular country or by the compulsory introduction of the state language. Scientific research results in the formation of concepts, programs, and methodological approaches for the implementation and functional development of the state language[2].

For this reason, there is a need to conduct a harmonious language policy in an independent state to ensure the wide use of the state language, study its importance in maintaining national identity, and ensure international stability. It is a socio-historical reality that in our country, in 1989, the Uzbek language was given the status of a state language, marking the beginning of its independent development as a sovereign state. "Each of us should consider attention to the state language as attention to independence, respect, and loyalty to the state language, respect, and loyalty to the Motherland, and make this view the rule of our lives," which requires the functional development of the Uzbek language and the search for effective ways of expansion. To fulfill this task, it is necessary to make the socio-philosophical factors of the functional development of the Uzbek language the subject of research[3].

Decrees such as No. PF-4947 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017, "On the strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan," No. PF-5850 dated October 21, 2019, "On measures to fundamentally increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as a state language," No. PF-5850, 2020 Decree No. PF-6084 dated October 20, 2019, "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language in our country and improve language policy," and PQ-4479 dated October 4, 2019, "On the wide celebration of the thirtieth anniversary of the adoption of the Law "On the State Language," serve to a certain

extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in the decree number and other regulatory legal documents related to the state language[4].

Many of these languages lack a writing system, with 80% of African language speakers not having their own writing system. This limits their use in education systems and on the internet, where English dominates 81% of content. While languages have historically appeared, evolved, and disappeared over time, the current rate of language extinction is unprecedented. Efforts to preserve endangered languages aim to maintain cultural and linguistic diversity, as language is crucial for preserving the culture and traditions of peoples worldwide[5].

According to Article 7 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the State Language," valid scientific rules and norms of the Uzbek literary language are observed in the spheres where the state language is officially used. The state ensures the enrichment and improvement of the Uzbek language, including the introduction of universally recognized scientific-technical and socio-political terms. Through this, the state has taken responsibility for the preservation, enrichment, and development of the Uzbek language.

On this basis, many scientific research projects on enriching and improving the Uzbek language are being carried out in Uzbekistan. Dictionaries and scientific treatises on various fields are regularly published. Currently, all publishing houses in the country are publishing materials that showcase the beauty of the native language. Documents are to be accepted and published in the state language, as specified in the fourth part of Article 26 of the Law "On the Procedure for Preparing Draft Laws and Submitting them to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan." According to this provision, "the draft law and the documents attached to it shall be submitted to the Legislative Chamber in the state language by the subjects of the right of legislative initiative."

The implementation of these norms can be seen in the example of the draft laws currently being submitted to the Legislative Chamber, as well as in the fact that laws being adopted in the Oliy Majlis are being intensively discussed in the Uzbek language.

However, there is wisdom in every event, and intellectuals, especially creative individuals, should reflect on the uproar over language issues. Each person should contribute to the further development of the native language, enriching its unique tones and revealing the richness inherent in the language. This is important so that in the future, our children, friends, and compatriots continue to speak Uzbek to each other[6].

Despite Uzbek being declared the state language, Russian is still widely used in government offices. The Uzbek language is not yet the language of inter-ethnic communication, and there is a perceived lack of resources and books in Uzbek. Many believe that the sudden transition to the Latin alphabet has caused damage to the language. In response, the nationwide movement "Yuksalish" has organized free courses for voluntary learners and other initiatives to promote and support the Uzbek language. One proposal is to create mobile applications aimed at teaching young people about language norms in an interactive way. These efforts are vital for the continued development and promotion of the Uzbek language.

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